

**North Carolina Division of Parks and Recreation
Department of Natural and Cultural Resources**

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**NORTH CAROLINA STATE PARKS SYSTEM
ANALYSIS OF VISITORS PER VEHICLE:
2023-2024 STUDY**

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INTRODUCTION

To estimate overall visitation to state park units in NC, the NC Division of Parks and Recreation (the Division) installs mechanical traffic counters at vehicular entrances to each park. Some parks have more than one traffic counter because they have multiple entrances for vehicles. Some parks also have trail counters to measure pedestrians, but not all pedestrian, bicycle or water entrances are counted. To estimate total visitation, a multiplier representing the estimated number of visitors in each vehicle is applied to the raw traffic counts observed at each park unit. These multipliers vary depending on the type of use and the season of the year. For example, traffic counters near boat launches have a lower multiplier in winter than in summer, and traffic counters near trailheads have a higher multiplier during peak use times, such as the fall season in the mountains. Multipliers have historically been based on observations made by park staff and volunteers and are adjusted to estimate for pedestrian, equestrian, water, and other accesses that do not have traffic counters.

In 2011, the N.C. General Assembly directed the Division to examine the number of visitors per vehicle (i.e., the multipliers) used in the calculation of visitor counts at state parks at least once every five years (S.L. 2012-93, see Appendix A). Since then, the Division has worked with the Department of Parks, Recreation & Tourism Management in the College of Natural Resources at North Carolina State University to set up a repeatable process for conducting a periodic visitors-per-vehicle assessment. The first study, conducted in 2013, evaluated visitation through intercept surveys collected from park visitors, considering non-vehicular access in the park as well as vehicle counts. The 2013 study, which focused on 15 park units, featured 2,014 visitor contacts and 1,746 completed surveys. The second study, conducted in 2018, counted the number of people in vehicles that entered a park and did not include a survey component. The 2018 study, which focused on 17 park units, included a total of 7,033 vehicles and 15,935 visitors counted. Based on those studies, the Division identified multipliers currently used to estimate visitation at different parks across the system (see Appendix B). The third iteration of this study- designed to validate and/or update these multiplier estimates - was conducted from Summer 2023 through Spring 2024. Results are presented in this report.

2. STUDY METHODS

We attempted to model our 2023-24 study after previous studies as closely as possible to facilitate comparisons. However, we made several notable changes. First, we elected to sample 12 focal parks across the state, ensuring coverage across different geographic regions (e.g., Mountains, Piedmont, or Coastal Plain) and visitation levels (e.g., high, moderate, and low). We specifically targeted many parks that had not been captured in earlier studies, helping to extend insights from previous years across the broader park system (Table 1, Figure 1). Maps of all parks that were sampled, including sampling locations, are included in Appendix C. We chose to sample fewer parks to increase the number of visits we could make (and the data we might collect) at each one. Second, all data collection occurred via brief exit surveys of vehicles leaving the park. This enabled us to combine the intercept survey approach (from 2013) and the visitor count approach (from 2018) into a single data collection method that maximized the information we could collect in a short period of time.

Figure 1. Map of NC State Parks included in 2023-2024 Visitors per Vehicle (VPV) Study

Table 1. NC state parks sampled across different visitors per vehicle (VPV) study years.

PARK	REGION	2013 STUDY	2018 STUDY	2023-2024 STUDY
TOTAL PARKS IN STUDY		15	17	12
BOB'S CREEK STATE NATURAL AREA	Mountains			
CAROLINA BEACH STATE PARK (CABE)	Coastal		X	X
CARVERS CREEK STATE PARK (CACR)	Coastal			X
CHIMNEY ROCK STATE PARK (CHRO)	Mountains	X	X	
CLIFFS OF THE NEUSE STATE PARK (CLNE)	Coastal		X	
CROWDERS MOUNTAIN STATE PARK (CRMO)	Piedmont		X	
DISMAL SWAMP STATE PARK	Coastal			
ELK KNOB STATE PARK (ELKN)	Mountains			X
ENO RIVER STATE PARK (ENRI)	Piedmont	X		X
FALLS LAKE STATE RECREATION AREA (FALA)	Piedmont		X	
FORT FISHER STATE RECREATION AREA (FOFI)	Coastal	X		
FORT MACON STATE PARK (FOMA)	Coastal	X	X	
GOOSE CREEK STATE PARK (GOCR)	Coastal		X	
GORGES STATE PARK (GORG)	Mountains	X	X	
GRANDFATHER MOUNTAIN STATE PARK (GRMO)	Mountains		X	
HAMMOCKS BEACH STATE PARK (HABE)	Coastal	X		X
HANGING ROCK STATE PARK (HARO)	Piedmont	X	X	
HAW RIVER STATE PARK	Piedmont			
JOCKEY'S RIDGE STATE PARK (JORI)	Coastal	X		X
JONES LAKE STATE PARK (JONE)	Coastal		X	
JORDAN LAKE STATE RECREATION AREA (JORD)	Piedmont	X		X
KERR LAKE STATE RECREATION AREA (KELA)	Piedmont	X	X	
LAKE JAMES STATE PARK (LAJA)	Mountains		X	
LAKE NORMAN STATE PARK (LANO)	Piedmont			X
LAKE WACCAMAW STATE PARK	Coastal			
LOWER HAW RIVER STATE NATURAL AREA	Piedmont			
LUMBER RIVER STATE PARK	Coastal			
MAYO RIVER STATE PARK	Piedmont			
MEDOC MOUNTAIN STATE PARK (MEMO)	Piedmont		X	
MERCHANTS MILLPOND STATE PARK (MEMI)	Coastal	X		X
MORROW MOUNTAIN STATE PARK (MOMO)	Piedmont	X		
MOUNT MITCHELL STATE PARK (MOMI)	Mountains	X	X	
NEW RIVER STATE PARK	Mountains			
OCCONEECHEE MOUNTAIN STATE NATURAL AREA (OMSN)	Piedmont			X
PETTIGREW STATE PARK	Coastal			
PILOT MOUNTAIN STATE PARK (PIMO)	Piedmont	X		
PISGAH VIEW STATE PARK	Mountains			
RAVEN ROCK STATE PARK (RARO)	Piedmont		X	
RENDEZVOUS MOUNTAIN STATE PARK	Mountains			
SINGLETERY LAKE STATE PARK	Coastal			
SOUTH MOUNTAINS STATE PARK (SOMO)	Mountains			X
STONE MOUNTAIN STATE PARK (STMO)	Mountains	X		X
WEYMOUTH WOODS-SANDHILLS NATURE PRESERVE	Piedmont			
WILLIAM B. UMSTEAD STATE PARK (WIUM)	Piedmont		X	

We visited each park at least once for a weekday and weekend for the summer 2023 season (June-Aug), fall 2023 season (October-December), and spring 2024 season (February 2024 - April 2024). To determine survey dates, we used an online random list generator with all of the park names. We adjusted the schedule as needed based on the student technician schedule. We avoided sampling during holiday weekends (e.g., Memorial Day weekend, Easter weekend, etc), as higher visitation during these weekends may not accurately represent typical visitation patterns. We also considered weather, as days of extreme heat or heavy precipitation might have impacted estimates. The sampling schedule for parks appears in Table 2.

Designated exit survey locations were selected by the Division and were located near traffic counters at different park entrances (see Appendix C for details). During each exit survey session, a trained NCSU student research assistant or pair of research assistants counted the number of vehicles exiting a park at a designated location for two hours. This two hour period typically occurred between 12:00pm-6:00pm. Researchers documented the number of visitors per vehicle (VPV) for every passing vehicle, and attempted to stop all exiting vehicles (or every n th vehicle if there was a need to minimize traffic delays) to ask the driver: 1) how many people are in the vehicle (adults and kids), 2) if the driver is visiting from NC (and if so, what county or ZIP code and if not, what state or country), 3) how much time they spent in the park, and 4) which zones in the park the group visited during their trip today (from a pre-specified list of zones)? The exit survey protocol is included in Appendix D, and the data collection sheet is included in Appendix E. During the interaction, researchers also observed the race/ethnicity of visitors. If a vehicle was a mixed-race group, 'other' was marked for this observation. Researchers also recorded all work vehicles exiting during this time window, and these vehicles were intentionally excluded in the VPV counts. The Results below describe key findings from these exit surveys, including VPV estimates across different parks and time periods, a summary of visitor demographics, and some preliminary findings regarding amenity and facility usage across different parks.

Table 2. Sampling schedule in NC state parks for 2023-24 visitors per vehicle study.

PARK	SUMMER 2023 SAMPLING	FALL 2023 SAMPLING	SPRING 2024 SAMPLING
CAROLINA BEACH	Monday (7/10), Sunday (7/9)	Friday (11/3), Saturday (11/4)	Sunday (2/25), Monday (2/26)
CARVERS CREEK	Friday (6/16), Saturday (6/17)	Friday (10/27), Saturday (10/28)	Monday (3/25), Wednesday (4/24), Saturday (2/24), Sunday (3/24)
ELK KNOB	Friday (7/21), Saturday (7/22)	Friday (10/27), Saturday (10/28)	Friday (4/12), Saturday (4/13)
ENO RIVER	Monday (7/10), Friday (7/7, 7/21), Saturday (7/8, 7/22), Sunday (7/9)	Friday (11/3), Saturday (11/4)	Friday (3/1), Saturday (3/2)
HAMMOCKS BEACH	Tuesday (6/20), Saturday (6/24), Sunday (6/25)	X Friday (10/20), Saturday (10/21)	Friday (4/21), Saturday (4/22)
JOCKEY'S RIDGE	Friday (7/28), Saturday (7/29)	Friday (9/29), Saturday (9/30)	Friday (4/19), Saturday (4/20)
JORDAN LAKE	Friday (6/9), Saturday (6/10)	Friday (12/1), Saturday (10/21)	Friday (3/22), Saturday (3/23)
LAKE NORMAN	Friday (8/11), Saturday (8/12)	Friday (11/17), Saturday (11/18)	Friday (4/26), Saturday (4/27)
MERCHANTS MILLPOND	Friday (7/28), Sunday (7/30)	Friday (10/13), Sunday (10/29)	Monday (3/11), Sunday (3/3),
OCCONEECHEE MOUNTAIN	Friday (7/7), Sunday (7/9)	Monday (11/13), Sunday (11/12),	Friday (3/8), Sunday (3/10)
SOUTH MOUNTAINS	Thursday (8/3), Friday (8/4)	Friday (10/20, 11/17), Saturday (10/21, 11/18)	Friday (4/19), Saturday (4/20)
STONE MOUNTAIN	Monday (7/24), Friday (7/14), Saturday (7/15)	Friday (10/13), Saturday (10/14)	Friday (4/12), Saturday (4/13)

When interpreting data in this report, several limitations should be considered:

1. Our data were primarily collected by twelve different undergraduate students with limited field experience, and these researchers might have made unanticipated errors. However, all researchers underwent a standardized training, and each paired up with mentors (e.g., project managers, more experienced field research assistants) during their first sessions to ensure that all protocols were being followed.
2. Our racial/ethnicity data was collected via observation. We recognize the limitations of these assumptions, as racial identity and ethnicity are not always observable. We opted for this approach (rather than self-reports) to minimize survey response time and reduce the potential for conflict with visitors who might not appreciate the race/ethnicity question.
3. Due to scheduling constraints, most of our exit survey sessions occurred on Fridays and Saturdays. Thus, certain types of visitors who tend to frequent parks on other days (e.g., Latinos on Sunday afternoons) are likely underrepresented in the samples.
4. Researchers did not consistently record the type of vehicle in this study (only visitor vehicle versus work vehicle). It is not clear, therefore, how vehicle counts at traffic counters (and multipliers) in certain parks with lakes (e.g., Lake Norman, Jordan Lake) might be affected by things such as boat trailers. Additional research and calibration may be needed to account for atypical vehicles with multiple axles.
5. Although the exit survey strategy centered on vehicular access captured most park visitors, the study did not effectively account for parks within the system that have multiple non-vehicular access points that substantially contribute to the park's visitation. For example, parks like Eno River and William B. Umstead have multiple vehicular access points as well as access by bicycles and pedestrians, and lake and river-based parks often have multiple boating access sites where visitation is not recorded.
6. Finally, it should be reiterated that the information in this report is not an exact measurement of actual park visitation. Weather and other conditions impact visitation, and these factors may limit the generalization of our visitor count numbers to other months (e.g., January) or other parks. As this study is repeated in the future, the information will become more useful for observing general visitation trends.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Visitors Per Vehicle Estimates

During 116 survey periods across 12 parks, our team counted a total of 5,529 visitor vehicles and 340 work vehicles (work vehicles were 5.8% of the total). Overall, we counted 11,734 visitors in vehicles. Overall, across all parks, days, and seasons, the average estimate for VPV was 2.12. Across all parks, VPV estimates were slightly higher on weekend days (2.19) than weekdays (1.98), and slightly higher during the peak summer visitation (2.25) than either the fall (2.07) or spring seasons (1.99). The highest VPV numbers were observed at Jockey’s Ridge (2.67) and Jordan Lake (2.49), while the lowest VPV numbers were at Carvers Creek (1.65) and Carolina Beach (1.71). Table 3 shows the results of the vehicle counts at all participating parks, comparing VPV across weekdays, weekends, and sampling seasons.

Table 3. Total vehicles counted and visitors per vehicle (VPV) estimates for 12 focal NC state parks, by day and by season.

PARK	VEHICLES COUNTED		VPV ESTIMATES*					
	WORK VEHICLES	VISITOR VEHICLES	OVERALL	WEEKDAYS	WEEKENDS	SUMMER	FALL	SPRING
CAROLINA BEACH	43	571	1.71	1.63	1.76	1.61	1.73	1.74
CARVERS CREEK	42	236	1.65	1.43	1.74	1.55	1.80	1.60
ELK KNOB	5	125	2.31	2.19	2.39	2.36	2.34	1.67
ENO RIVER	27	675	1.95	1.82	2.04	2.01	1.94	1.75
HAMMOCKS BEACH	20	307	2.08	2.12	2.06	2.38	1.70	1.50
JOCKEY’S RIDGE	28	467	2.68	2.67	2.69	2.70	2.80	2.58
JORDAN LAKE	46	645	2.49	2.22	2.59	2.68	1.99	1.89
LAKE NORMAN	46	852	1.97	1.80	2.03	2.03	1.78	2.07
MERCHANTS MILLPOND	21	75	2.12	2.38	1.96	2.00	2.28	1.92
OCCONEECHEE MOUNTAIN	14	241	1.85	1.37	2.05	1.64	1.94	1.92
SOUTH MOUNTAINS	35	753	2.24	2.08	2.28	2.21	2.24	2.32
STONE MOUNTAIN	13	582	2.23	2.15	2.29	2.26	2.28	2.05
TOTAL	340	5,529	2.12	1.98	2.19	2.25	2.07	1.99

*The number of visitors per vehicle was only estimated for visitor vehicles, not work vehicles

3.2. Amenity and Facility Usage

Of all visitor vehicles counted we conducted exit surveys for 4,619 vehicles, resulting in an 83.5% response rate. Responses from visitors in these vehicles were used to estimate park usage patterns and visitor demographics.

Overall, visits greater than or equal to 24 hours (overnight visits) accounted for 3.5% of all reported state park visits (n = 170). For parks with campgrounds, overnight use accounted for 5.3% of reported park use, though not all campground access points were surveyed (for example, Jordan Lake has multiple campgrounds and no exit surveys at Jordan Lake occurred at campground exits). The overall average time in park for visits greater than or equal to 24 hours was 2.3 days, with a median of 1.5 days. For day visitors to state parks (n = 4,438), the overall average time in the park was 1.98 hours, with a median of 2 hours. Overnight use of the park did not vary much across seasons but tended to be slightly less common – relative to day use - on weekend days. The average time in park for day users tended to be higher on weekend days (2.04 hours vs. 1.85 hours), while the average time for park for overnight users tended to be higher on weekdays than weekends (3.0 days vs. 1.8 days).

Amenity use was recorded for 4,402 vehicles. Across all parks, our estimates of amenity usage showed the most popular features were trails (use reported by 61.6% of visitors), natural features unique to each park such as the sand dune at Jockey's Ridge or the river at Eno River (18.4%), lakes and/or beaches (17.0%), and visitor centers (17.15%). Trail use was proportionally highest at for Elk Knob (94.7%), Occoneechee (93.4%), and Carvers Creek (91.9%). True visitor centers, which were not present at all parks, were visited most frequently at Jockey's Ridge (33.1%), Merchant's Millpond (30.2%), and Lake Norman (25.9%). A summary of amenity usage by park appears in Table 4.

Table 4. Percentage of NC state park visitor vehicles reporting amenity usage across 12 focal parks.

PARK	TOTAL VEHICLES RESPONDING	VISITOR CENTER	CAMPGROUND	BEACH/LAKE	PICNIC AREA	TRAIL	NATURAL FEATURE*
CAROLINA BEACH	474	17.7	11.2	24.3	4.6	58.4	1.5
CARVERS CREEK	184	14.7	0.0	0.0	6.5	91.9	10.9
ELK KNOB	113	8.0	0.0	0.0	3.5	94.7	17.7
ENO RIVER	535	16.5	1.1	0.0	7.3	81.5	27.9
HAMMOCKS BEACH	239	25.1	2.5	38.9	6.7	38.5	0.8
JOCKEY'S RIDGE	344	33.1	0.0	3.5	2.9	16.0	84.3
JORDAN LAKE	462	9.1	2.6	63.9	14.5	22.9	0.0
LAKE NORMAN	673	25.9	6.5	34.8	11.0	53.9	0.0
MERCHANTS MILLPOND	63	30.2	17.5	0.0	28.6	61.9	20.6
OCCONEECHEE MOUNTAIN	213	7.5	0.0	0.0	3.8	93.4	11.3
SOUTH MOUNTAINS	622	12.2	3.7	0.0	2.4	81.2	28.5
STONE MOUNTAIN	480	9.8	12.5	0.0	1.9	75.4	23.5
TOTAL	4,402	17.2	4.9	17.0	6.7	61.6	18.4

*Natural feature refers to the unique natural feature that many parks were built around, such as the sand dune at Jockey's Ridge, the mountain at Stone Mountain, or the river at Eno River.

NOTE: Not all parks contained all facilities (e.g., many did not have campgrounds or beaches/lakes).

Amenity usage patterns shifted slightly based on days of the week and seasons. On weekdays and weekends, the most popular amenities were trails and natural features. For weekdays, trails were slightly less popular (59.4% of vehicles reported using them) when compared to weekends (62.6%). Natural features were slightly more popular on weekdays (21.7% of vehicles reported) when compared to weekends (19.9%). During the summer season, trails remained most popular (50.0% of vehicles reported using them), though less popular than in fall (66.9%) or spring seasons (70.4%). Beaches and lakes (28.5%) and picnic areas (7.5%) were slightly more popular during the summer than in other seasons. Natural features were more frequently visited in the fall (21.7%) and summer (19.6%) than in the spring (13.0%). Visitor centers were used more often in the spring (23.6%) and fall (21.3%) than in the summer (8.5%).

3.3. Visitor Demographics

Age

Of all the vehicles counted at state parks, approximately 78.3% contained adults only (age 18 or older) and 21.7% traveled with children under the age of 18. The ratio of vehicles containing youth visiting state parks was higher on weekend days (23.1%) as opposed to weekdays (18.9%). Youth visitation rates were also higher during the summer months (28.7% of vehicles containing youth) compared to spring (17.5%) or fall (16.6%). Table 5 shows the percentage of total visitors, not vehicles, counted at each park who were estimated to be under the age of 18 years old.

Vehicles with youth had a higher VPV estimate (3.53) than vehicles with adults only (1.73). Overall, there was not a significant difference between vehicles with adults only and those with youth in terms of hours spent in the park. The most popular amenities for groups with youth included trails (used by 44.7% of vehicles with kids), natural features (24.5%), beaches (17.3%), and visitor centers (11.7%). Trails were less likely to be used by vehicles with youth than vehicles with adults only, whereas natural areas, visitor centers, beaches/lakes, and picnic zones were all more likely to be used by vehicles with youth.

Table 5. Percentage of NC state park visitors under the age of 18 years old, by park.

PARK	VISITORS COUNTED	VISITORS UNDER AGE 18 (%)*
CAROLINA BEACH	974	9.1%
CARVERS CREEK	390	11.5%
ELK KNOB	289	10.0%
ENO RIVER	1,314	19.6%
HAMMOCKS BEACH	640	22.8%
JOCKEY'S RIDGE	1253	18.8%
JORDAN LAKE	1,603	24.1%
LAKE NORMAN	1,680	15.7%
MERCHANTS MILLPOND	159	28.9%
OCCONEECHEE MOUNTAIN	445	14.2%
SOUTH MOUNTAINS	1,688	19.1%
STONE MOUNTAIN	1,299	14.9%
TOTAL	11,734	17.7%

*Estimates were based on observations of youth vs. adults during exit survey counts.

Race/Ethnicity

We were able to record visitors' race/ethnicity in 5,437 vehicles. Based on these observations, we determined that across all parks, 79.2% of visitors were White, 4.3% were Black, 5.48% were Latino, 3.4% were Asian, and 7.6% were Mixed race or other. The proportion of White visitors was higher on weekdays (84.8%) than weekend days (76.5%), while the proportion of Latino (6.3% vs. 3.8%) and Asian visitors (4.2% vs. 1.8%) was much higher on weekends than weekdays. The summer season was also more diverse racially. In the summer, 75.6% of visitors were White, compared to 84.5% of visitors during spring and 78.3% in the spring season. We also observed higher percentages of Black visitors (4.7% vs 4.3% overall), Latino visitors (8.1% vs. 5.5% overall), and Asian visitors (3.9% vs. 3.4% overall) during the summer. Table 6 shows the percentage of vehicles containing visitors from different racial/ethnic groups.

Table 6. Percentage of NC State Park vehicles containing visitors from different racial/ethnic groups, by park.

PARK	VEHICLES COUNTED*	WHITE (%)	BLACK (%)	LATINO (%)	ASIAN (%)	OTHER/ MIXED (%)
CAROLINA BEACH	525	93.6	1.8	2.0	0.4	2.3
CARVERS CREEK	235	72.8	11.9	4.7	3.8	6.8
ELK KNOB	120	88.3	0.0	0.8	1.7	9.2
ENO RIVER	663	73.3	3.5	6.2	5.3	11.8
HAMMOCKS BEACH	304	85.9	6.3	2.3	0.7	4.9
JOCKEYS RIDGE	464	87.7	1.1	2.4	1.7	7.1
JORDAN LAKE	606	62.9	6.4	13.7	6.6	10.4
LAKE NORMAN STATE PARK	841	76.5	5.8	7.6	3.1	7.0
MERCHANTS MILLPOND	75	92.0	4.0	0.0	0.0	4.0
OCCONEECHEE	239	74.9	4.2	5.4	5.9	9.6
SOUTH MOUNTAINS	748	76.6	5.2	4.9	4.0	9.2
STONE MOUNTAIN	581	87.1	1.7	3.3	3.1	4.8
GRAND TOTAL	5437	79.2	4.3	5.5	3.4	7.6

*Estimates were based on observation of race/ethnicity during exit survey counts. The "Other" category includes vehicles with mixed-race occupants, or a combination of different races/ethnicities. Race/ethnicity was not counted for all visitors.

VPV varied significantly across race/ethnicity. The highest means were for vehicles with Latino visitors (2.62) and Asian visitors (2.53), and the lowest means were for vehicles of Black visitors (1.99) and white visitors (2.03). Time in the park did not differ significantly across racial/ethnic groups, although Black visitors (0.4%) and Latino visitors (1.3%) displayed the lowest ratios of overnight visitors. Certain amenities appealed to some racial/ethnic groups more than others. For example, visitors of color - especially Black and Latino visitors - were more likely to frequent beach/lake amenities than their white counterparts, while white and Asian visitors were most likely to use trails or campgrounds. Use of natural features were approximately equal across all groups.

Place of Origin

We were able to record the place of origin for visitors in 4,619 vehicles. Based on these responses, we determined that 84.7% of vehicles contained visitors who were from NC, and 15.3% were from out-of-state. The proportion of vehicles from out-of-state was higher on weekdays (20.0%) than weekends (12.9%). The proportion of out-of-state vehicles was slightly higher in the fall (16.3%) and spring (16.2%) compared to summer (13.6%). We found that certain parks attracted more out-of-state visitors than others. Merchant's Millpond and Jockey's Ridge attract out-of-state visitors, while Carvers Creek, Jordan Lake, and Eno River appealed more to in-state visitors. Across all surveyed vehicles, 34.3% reported a local county residency (bordering the state park), whereas 50.4% reported residency from a non-local North Carolina county. Local visitation was more common during weekdays than weekends (38.3% vs. 32.3%), and slightly more common during spring (36.6%) as opposed to fall (34.4%) and summer (32.3%). Local visitors were most common at Carolina Beach (68.3%) and Eno River (67.5%) and least common at Jockey's Ridge (8.0%) and South Mountains (7.9%). Table 7 shows the breakdown of visitor vehicles by in-state (local or non-local county) and out-of-state.

Table 7. Percentage of NC State Park vehicles from NC (local or non-local county) or out-of-state, by park.

PARK	TOTAL VEHICLES WITH ORIGIN RECORDED	VEHICLES FROM LOCAL NC COUNTY (%)*	VEHICLES FROM NON-LOCAL NC COUNTY (%)	VEHICLES FROM OUT-OF-STATE (%)
CAROLINA BEACH	502	68.3	22.7	9.0
CARVERS CREEK	189	17.5	76.7	5.8
ELK KNOB	116	27.6	62.9	9.5
ENO RIVER	545	67.5	26.2	6.2
HAMMOCKS BEACH	260	56.5	30.4	13.1
JOCKEYS RIDGE	390	8.0	25.6	66.4
JORDAN LAKE	471	14.7	78.6	6.8
LAKE NORMAN STATE PARK	730	45.6	41.1	13.3
MERCHANTS MILLPOND	65	18.5	38.5	43.1
OCCONEECHEE	218	43.1	50.9	6.0
SOUTH MOUNTAINS	642	7.9	80.7	11.4
STONE MOUNTAIN	491	14.3	71.7	14.1
TOTAL	4619	34.3	50.4	15.3

*A local county was defined as any county where a state park was located or a county bordering at least one side of a state park.

Out-of-state vehicles had a higher VPV (2.51) estimate than in-state vehicles (2.10). Overall, out-of-state vehicles spent more hours in state parks (5.25) as compared to in-state vehicles (3.70). The most popular amenities used by out-of-state residents generally mirrored those of in-state visitors. However, out-of-state vehicles reported proportionally higher use of natural features (34.0% for out-of-state vs. 14.5% for in-state), campgrounds (7.4% vs. 4.1%), and visitor centers (20.7% vs. 15.5%), while in-state visitors reported proportionally higher use of trails (61.3% for in-state vs. 42.2% for out-of-state) and beaches and lakes (16.7% vs. 12.6%).

4. RECOMMENDATIONS

Overall, the VPV estimates from the 2023-24 study (2.12) were slightly lower than the estimates generated in either 2018 (2.3) or 2013 (3.0). This could be due to several factors. The COVID-19 pandemic altered the way people travel and engage in outdoor recreation, with social distancing practices altering behavior norms. Perhaps larger carpools have become less common in the wake of the pandemic. Variation might also be due to the different parks that were sampled. Only 6 parks sampled in 2023-24 (Carolina Beach, Eno River, Hammock’s Beach, Jordan Lake, Merchant’s Millpond, and Stone Mountain) were also sampled in previous years (mostly in 2013), and visitor use patterns in the new parks might look different. However, it should be noted that, for all of the repeatedly sampled parks, 2023-24 VPV estimates were lower than in previous years (Table 8). The variation might also be due to the slightly different sampling approach: exit surveys of vehicles leaving the park. This approach to counting visitors was similar to the one employed in 2018, but quite different (and likely more accurate and comprehensive) than the one employed in 2013. Other potential sources of variation include weather (visitation is likely to be lower on colder or rainy days) and the survey day itself (a majority of 2023-24 observation sessions occurred on Fridays and Saturdays, and previous surveys featured a greater variety of sampling days).

Table 8. Comparison of visitor per vehicle (VPV) estimates for parks in 2023-24 study and VPV estimates for the same parks in either the 2013 study, the 2018 study, or the current numbers used by NC State Parks to estimate visitation.

PARK	2013 STUDY	2018 STUDY	CURRENT MULTIPLIER	2023-24 STUDY
CAROLINA BEACH		2.3	4	1.71
CARVERS CREEK			3 (weekdays) 4 (weekends)	1.65
ELK KNOB			2	2.31
ENO RIVER	2.3		3.5	1.95
HAMMOCK'S BEACH	3.1		3	2.08
JOCKEY'S RIDGE	3.5		3	2.68
JORDAN LAKE	3.7		4 (summer, spring, fall) 2 (winter)	2.49
LAKE NORMAN			3	1.97
MERCHANTS MILLPOND	2.5		3	2.12
OCCONEECHEE MOUNTAIN			3.5	1.85
SOUTH MOUNTAINS			4	2.24
STONE MOUNTAIN	2.6		4	2.23
TOTAL	3.0	2.3		2.12

As noted in previous vehicle count reports, it should be reiterated that any method of measuring attendance is only an estimate. Future studies could include more parks and more sampling days or locations, but they would still represent a small subsample of actual visitors. The importance of measuring visitation is to understand trends over time - particularly between similar locations. This study's results can be used to evaluate the accuracy of the current VPV estimates (and multipliers) developed by the Division to estimate attendance at our focal parks, but they should be cautiously interpreted when applied to similar parks not studied here. For example, multipliers for different days and seasons at Jordan Lake might be comparable to Falls Lake, but more research is needed to confirm that. Reliability of these data will be improved with additional sampling in future years, potentially accounting for factors such as weather and the socio-demographic attributes of visitors reported here.

One novel element - and major advantage - of the 2023-24 study was our ability to estimate visitors' demographic attributes based on exit survey responses. For instance, we were able to show that, across all parks we studied, 78.3% of visitors were adults, most (79.2%) were White, and a majority (84.7%) were from NC. We also found that trails were, by far, the most popular amenity in parks - used by 61% of visitors across all parks. These types of questions could be added to future exit surveys to help park managers understand not only how many people are coming to parks, but who these people are and how they are using parks.

Moving forward, we recommend the following additions and adjustments to vehicle count studies in NC State Parks (many of which were echoed in previous reports):

- Consistently sample some of the same parks every 5 years using the same counting methods (e.g., exit surveys) to accurately assess trends in VPV estimates over time.
- Sample more parks units and expand sampling times to include a greater variety of days and seasons.
- Consider visitors entering parks via other modes of transportation (i.e., those who do not enter on roads with traffic counters) such as trails and adjust VPV estimates upward slightly to account for these other modes of park access.
- Integrate other methods of tracking visitors such as mobile tracking data and use comparison studies to determine how these alternative approaches compare to more conventional traffic counter data/estimates (see separate 2025 report on Mobile Tracking of state park visitation).

Collectively, these various approaches should help Division staff determine optimal strategies for estimating visitation, including but not limited to VPV counts.

APPENDIX A. Legislation mandating Visitor Per Vehicle Counts.

**GENERAL ASSEMBLY OF NORTH CAROLINA
SESSION 2011**

**SESSION LAW 2012-93
SENATE BILL 813**

AN ACT TO REQUIRE THE DEPARTMENT OF CULTURAL RESOURCES AND THE DEPARTMENT OF ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES TO STUDY VARIOUS REVENUE ENHANCEMENTS AND POTENTIAL SAVINGS AT STATE HISTORIC SITES AND MUSEUMS, THE STATE ZOO, STATE PARKS, AND STATE AQUARIUMS, AS RECOMMENDED BY THE JOINT LEGISLATIVE PROGRAM EVALUATION OVERSIGHT COMMITTEE.

The General Assembly of North Carolina enacts:

SECTION 1. The Department of Cultural Resources shall implement the following recommendations:

- (1) Study site proximity and span of control to identify historic sites that could adopt a coordinated management structure and report no later than December 15, 2012, to the Senate Appropriations Committee on General Government and Information Technology and the House Appropriations Committee on General Government.
- (2) Study reduced schedules for historic sites and report no later than December 15, 2012, to the Senate Appropriations Committee on General Government and Information Technology and the House Appropriations Committee on General Government.
- (3) Study the feasibility of implementing more reliable mechanisms for counting visitors and report no later than December 15, 2012, to the Senate Appropriations Committee on General Government and Information Technology and the House Appropriations Committee on General Government.
- (4) Determine the appropriate operating schedule for the Richard Caswell Memorial after the CSS Neuse moves to its new location.
- (5) Study potential savings from introducing and expanding admission fees; eliminating discounts or raising fees; adopting corporate sponsorship for some sites; and transferring operations to nonprofit support groups, municipalities, or other appropriate entities and report no later than December 15, 2012, to the Senate Appropriations Committee on General Government and Information Technology and the House Appropriations Committee on General Government. The report should specifically address potential savings at the following historic sites:
 - a. Alamance Battleground.
 - b. Aycock Birthplace.
 - c. Bennett Place.
 - d. Bentonville Battlefield.
 - e. Charlotte Hawkins Brown Memorial.
 - f. Duke Homestead.
 - g. Historic Edenton.
 - h. Historic Stagville.
 - i. Museum of the Albemarle.
 - j. Thomas Wolfe Memorial.
 - k. Town Creek Indian Mound.

SECTION 2. The Department of Environment and Natural Resources shall implement the following recommendations:

APPENDIX A. Legislation mandating Visitor Per Vehicle Counts. (Continued)

- (1) Study site proximity and span of control to identify parks that could adopt a coordinated management structure and report no later than December 15, 2012, to the House Appropriations Subcommittee on Natural and Economic Resources and the Senate Appropriations Committee on Natural and Economic Resources.
- (2) Study daily visitation data to determine potential changes from daily or seasonal closure of specific parks and report no later than December 15, 2012, to the House Appropriations Subcommittee on Natural and Economic Resources and the Senate Appropriations Committee on Natural and Economic Resources.
- (3) Validate no less frequently than every five years the number of visitors per car used in the calculation of visitor counts at State parks. The first report on this analysis shall be presented to the House Appropriations Subcommittee on Natural and Economic Resources and the Senate Appropriations Committee on Natural and Economic Resources no later than October 1, 2013.
- (4) Provide an analysis of anticipated State costs and savings from partnering with nonprofits for operations at the zoo and aquariums and recommendations for partnering based on the analysis no later than December 15, 2012, to the House Appropriations Subcommittee on Natural and Economic Resources and the Senate Appropriations Committee on Natural and Economic Resources.
- (5) Study and report no later than December 15, 2012, to the House Appropriations Subcommittee on Natural and Economic Resources and the Senate Appropriations Committee on Natural and Economic Resources regarding potential savings from each of the following changes:
 - a. Introducing or expanding admissions fees, eliminating discounts, or raising fees.
 - b. Adopting corporate sponsorship for some sites.
 - c. Transferring operations to nonprofit support groups, municipalities, or other appropriate entities.

SECTION 3. This act is effective when it becomes law.
In the General Assembly read three times and ratified this the 21st day of June,

2012.

s/ Walter H. Dalton
President of the Senate

s/ Thom Tillis
Speaker of the House of Representatives

s/ Beverly E. Perdue
Governor

Approved 1:40 p.m. this 28th day of June, 2012

APPENDIX B. Current Visitor per Vehicle (VPV) Multipliers used in all NC State Parks.

PARK	NUMBER OF TRAFFIC COUNTERS	MULTIPLIER FOR CARS	MULTIPLIER FOR BUSES	COMMENTS
Carolina Beach SP	1	4	30	Boaters and auditorium use based on actual numbers and permits.
Carvers Creek SP	1	Weekdays x 3 Weekends, holidays x 4	None	
Chimney Rock SP	1 Rumbling Bald Climbing Access	2	None	Attendance at Chimney Rock access is actual count by contractor. Rumbling Bald uses traffic counter plus backcountry registrations. Eagle Rock uses on-line reservations and backcountry registration.
Cliffs of the Neuse SP	1	4 during summer and weekends, 2 in winter	30	
Crowders Mountain SP	3	4 on weekends, 3 on weekdays	None	
Dismal Swamp SP	1	3	30	Nomadic counter used to calculate numbers.
Elk Knob SP	1	2	30	
Eno River SP	4	3.5	None	
Falls Lake SRA	8	March - Sept: Park Areas x 4 Park Office x 4 Rollingview Marina x 2 Oct-February: Park Areas x 2 Park Office x 2 Rollingview Marina x 2	None	
Fort Fisher SRA	2	4	30	
Fort Macon SP	2	4	30	
Goose Creek SP	2	Main entrance x 3 Dinah's Landing x2	30 or Actual	
Gorges SP	2	3	30	

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Dismal Swamp SP	1	3	30	Nomadic counter used to calculate numbers.
Elk Knob SP	1	2	30	
Eno River SP	4	3.5	None	
Falls Lake SRA	8	March - Sept: Park Areas x 4 Park Office x 4 Rollingview Marina x 2 Oct-February: Park Areas x 2 Park Office x 2 Rollingview Marina x 2	None	
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Goose Creek SP	2	Main entrance x 3 Dinah's Landing x2	30 or Actual	
Gorges SP	2	3	30	

APPENDIX B. Current Visitor per Vehicle (VPV) Multipliers used in all NC State Parks.

PARK	NUMBER OF TRAFFIC COUNTERS	MULTIPLIER FOR CARS	MULTIPLIER FOR BUSES	COMMENTS
Grandfather Mountain SP	5 Trail Counters	None	None	Trail counters at each trailhead for actual hiker count. Camper count from self-registration forms.
Hammocks Beach SP	1	3	None	Sep-May, 4 people per day, and Jun-Aug, 40 people per day added for personal boat traffic to Bear Island.
Hanging Rock SP	6	3.5	None	No counter at Vade Mecum.
Haw River SP	0	None	None	Numbers calculated by conference attendance totals plus other guests that sign in at the front desk.
Jockey's Ridge SP	2	3	30	
Jones Lake SP	1	4	30	
Jordan Lake SRA	11	4 from Mar-Oct 2 from Nov-Feb	30	Total for office area uses no multiplier.
Kerr Lake SRA	9	4	None	
Lake James SP	4	3.5 at park entrances 2 at boat ramps	30	
Lake Norman SP	2	3	None	
Lake Waccamaw SP	3	4	30	
Lumber River SP	2	4	None	Plus equestrians depending on size of monthly trail rides.
Mayo River SP	4	3	30 or Actual	
Medoc Mountain SP	2	4	30	
Merchants Millpond SP	3	3	30 or Actual	
Morrow Mountain SP	1	4	30	
Mt. Jefferson SNA	1	2	30	
Mount Mitchell SP	1	3.5	30 or Actual	
New River SP	3	221 Access x 4 Wagoner Rd x 2 Kings Creek x 2 (Apr-Oct)	30 or Actual	Plus 62 each day Apr-Oct for outfitter traffic.
Occoneechee Mountain SNA	1	3.5	None	
Pettigrew SP	2	3	30	

APPENDIX B. Current Visitor per Vehicle (VPV) Multipliers used in all NC State Parks.

PARK	NUMBER OF TRAFFIC COUNTERS	MULTIPLIER FOR CARS	MULTIPLIER FOR BUSES	COMMENTS
Pilot Mountain SP	3	4	None	No reliable way to track bus traffic, but bus traffic to mountain section is significant, buses to river section minimal.
Raven Rock SP	2	Mar - Nov: Weekdays x 3 Weekends x 4 South side, x 3 North side Dec - Feb: Weekdays x 2 Weekends x 4 South side, x 2 North side	30	
Singletary Lake SP	1	4	15, 30 or Actua	Visitation determined by group camp occupancy, plus vehicle count above the number of campers logged in. Visitation to satellite lakes not recorded.
South Mountains SP	1	4	30	No traffic counters at Clear Creek, Roper Hollow, Baptist Camp, or Watershed Rd.
Stone Mountain SP	2	4	None	
Weymouth Woods SNA	1	2	None	No traffic counters at Boyd tract or Paint Hill tract.
William B. Umstead SP	2	2		Plus 2 infrared counters at walk-in trails.

APPENDIX C. Maps of State Parks featured in 2023-24 study

Carolina Beach Access Points and Exit Survey Location

Carvers Creek Access Points and Exit Survey Locations

Elk Knob Access Points and Exit Survey Locations

Eno River Access Points and Exit Survey Locations

Hammocks Beach Access Points and Exit Survey Locations

HAMMOCKS BEACH STATE PARK

1572 Hammocks Beach Rd., Swansboro, NC 28584 Office: 910-326-4881
 hammocks.beach@ncparks.gov

Jordan Lake Access Points and Exit Survey Locations

Jordan Lake Access Points and Exit Survey Locations (Continued)

Jockey's Ridge Access Points and Exit Survey Locations

Lake Norman Access Points and Exit Survey Locations

Merchants Millpond Access Points and Exit Survey Locations

Occoneechee Mountain Access Points and Exit Survey Locations

OCCONEECHEE MOUNTAIN STATE NATURAL AREA

South Mountains Access Points and Exit Survey Locations

Stone Mountain Access Points and Exit Survey Locations

APPENDIX D. Exit Survey Protocol

NC State Park Exit Survey Protocol

The researcher(s) will wait at the park exit(s) and stop every vehicle departing the park during a designated 2-hour time block. If traffic levels are high, the researcher may choose to select every 2nd, 3rd, or nth vehicle leaving the park to avoid traffic bottlenecks. If the randomly selected vehicle is a park staff member or a service vehicle (e.g., delivery truck), or if the visitor's vehicle does not stop, then survey the next car instead. For EVERY vehicle that exits, always record the number of people in the car and note whether the vehicle is a visitor or service/work vehicle (there should be one row per vehicle on the data sheet). Additional information will be recorded for cars that engage with the exit survey process below:

1. Introduce yourself to an adult in the front seat as follows:

“Hi. I am a student researcher at NC State University and we are working with NC State Parks to learn a little more about who is visiting parks and why. Do you mind if I ask you a couple of quick questions about your visit to the park today? It'll only take a minute.”

[Wait for response and obtain informed consent before progressing.]

“Before we begin, please note that all of your responses are confidential, and your participation is completely voluntary. Would you like any more information about the study before proceeding?”

[If they say yes, you share a copy of the Study Information Sheet with them before proceeding.]

2. Ask the following questions of the driver or front seat passenger in the vehicle and record responses on the data sheet...

a) ASK: How many people are in your car today? How many adults? How many kids? [Also record race/ethnicity.] When asking these questions, you should also attempt to document (without asking directly) the race/ethnicity of the vehicle occupants as best you can using the following categories: White, Black, Latinx, Asian, Mixed/other. If it is impossible to tell or if the group is composed of a variety of races and ethnicities, check Mixed/other. If you do not feel comfortable estimating race/ethnicity based on physical appearance, you are welcome to ask the vehicle occupants to self-report... just know this might start a longer, more difficult conversation.

b) ASK: Are you from NC? If so, what county in NC? If not, what state (or country, if outside US)?

c) ASK: How much time did you spend in the park today? Record responses in number of hours (for day visitors) and number of nights (for overnight visitors), clearly noting number of nights if overnight (e.g., 2n) to distinguish that number from hours (e.g., 4.5). All responses will be recorded as hours (e.g., 48 hours for 2 nights) when data are entered later. If the respondent says they'll be coming back later, ask them how much time they plan to spend in the park today (or how many nights if an overnight visitor).

d) ASK: Which areas of the park did you (and your group) visit today? Record responses (with an “X” or check) based on a list of pre-specified activity zones present in most parks including visitor center/facilities, campgrounds, beach/lake areas, picnic areas, courts/fields, trails, significant historical features (e.g., old mill), and significant natural features (e.g., river, mountain). If other areas are utilized (playgrounds, etc.) note this in the “Other/Notes” column. You can also add any other notes about the exit survey or your interaction with the visitor(s) in that last column.

3. Conclude the interaction as follows:

“Thanks for answering my questions. I hope you enjoyed your visit today, and we hope to see you back at the park again soon.”

During and/or after each interaction, be sure to record all responses on the exit survey data sheet before moving on to survey people in the next car. And don't forget to record the number of people and type of vehicle (e.g., visitor or service/work vehicle) for ALL of the exiting cars that you don't survey too.

Park Name: _____ Observer: _____ Start Time: _____ End Time: _____ Current Temp: _____
 Weather Condition: - Sunny - Partly Sunny - Cloudy - Rainy

PAGE ____ OF ____

Row	COUNTS		PPL AGE		PPL RACE/ETHNICITY			PPL RESIDENCY		TIME IN PARK (hrs / nights)	MAIN ACTIVITY ZONES						OTHER / NOTES					
	Work Truck obs	Car obs	<18	>= 18	W	B	L	A	Mix		NC (County)	State (out-of-state)	Country (internat.)	VC/Fac	Ca m	Be/Lak		Pic	Ct/Fd	Tr	Hist. Area	Nat. Feat.
1																						
2																						
3																						
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Car Obs OR Work Truck Obs:
 select one
 Work Truck - includes official park, ranger, or state vehicles
 - includes FedEx, UPS, or other service/delivery vehicles

Race/Ethnicity codes:
 W = White
 B = Black
 L = Latinx
 A = Asian
 O/M = Other or Mixed race group

Time in Park:
 total # of hour or nights (specify) spent in park

Main Activity Zones:
 VC/Fac = Visitor Center or Facilities
 Cam = Campgrounds
 Be/Lak = Beach or Lake Area
 Pic = Picnic Area
 Ct/Fd = Court or Fields
 Tr = Trails
 Hist. Area = Historic Area or Feature (e.g. old water mill)
 Nat. Feat. = Natural Feature (e.g. dunes, mountain)

Other/Notes:
 Use for activity clarifications (e.g. playground) or other notes you think are important to record during data collection

